

Corporate governance revisited: Exploring the effect of family control on dividend policy in the Moroccan context

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Abstract :

Our study is designed to grasp the effect of family control on dividend policy of Moroccan listed firms by using longitudinal data spanning the period (2019-2023). Our results indicate and confirm the main hypothesis that family control has a negative significant impact on dividend payout in the Moroccan context. Regarding corporate governance variables, ownership concentration, board size, independence and CEO duality are determinants of dividend payout, while board gender diversity failed to record statistical significance. Additionally, the vast majority of control variables demonstrate significant impacts in the expected sign except for external audit quality and growth opportunities. For robustness checks, we use Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) estimator to deal with potential issues related to heteroscedasticity, moreover, we investigate the decision to pay dividends by using probit and logistic regression models. Regarding research limitations, we can state that our proxy of family control could be replaced by the percentage of ownership held by family members in order to stress the importance of addressing the non-linearity effect. Another limitation is related to the sample size; indeed, it is worth noting that the interpretation of our results should be done with caution. For research avenues, we suggest that future studies should consider the moderating effect of agency costs of free cash flow, growth opportunities, financial constraints, R&D investment expenditures and extend the sample by including other countries belonging to the MENA region in order to ensure the robustness of the empirical results.

Keywords: Corporate governance, Family control, Board of directors, Dividend policy, Agency costs, Morocco.

1. Introduction:

The research linking corporate governance to dividend payouts has garnered a flourishing interest by multiple scholars around the world (Abor & Fiador, 2013; Al-Najjar & Kilincarslan, 2016; Farinha, 2003; Gugler & Yurtoglu, 2003; Jiraporn et al., 2011; Mitton, 2004; Sener & Akben Selcuk, 2019; Setia-Atmaja et al., 2009). Economics qualify dividend policy as a mystery and an unresolved empirical puzzle (Easterbrook, 1984). Drawing from different theoretical frameworks, dividend payments are perceived both as a signaling mechanism about the management's expectations of future earnings, a device to alleviate or decrease agency costs by reducing free cash flow available for potential discretionary use and an effective instrument designed to align interests between outside and inside shareholder. In this wake, dividend payouts triggers and encourage the firm to interact with the market, in other words, the company must preserve, protect its reputation and ensure a good treatment of different shareholders in order to get access to the market for external funding opportunities (Aivazian et al., 2003; Faccio et al., 2001; Jensen, 1986; Jiraporn & Chintrakarn, 2009; La Porta et al., 2000; Setia-Atmaja, 2010; Truong & Heaney, 2007). The empirical evidence on divided policy strategies in family firms are mixed and still ambiguous across multiple markets (Setia-Atmaja et al., 2009). Furthermore, the agency-driven inefficiencies and conflicts related to over investment or dividend polices are more relevant and common among family corporations and partnerships (Fama & Jensen, 1985). Therefore, our study aims to extend the debate and tackle the gap by exploring this research question in a specify emerging market, where high ownership concentration levels are predominant (Jabbouri & Naili, 2019; Lakssoumi & Moussa, 2022; Louziri & Oubal, 2025). The study is structured as follow: the first section provides a literature review to summarize empirical insights conducted in different contexts, the second section describes the data gathering process and the methodology adopted, the section 3 outlines the results' analysis and discussion and lastly we will draw conclusions in order to assess the empirical study's limitations and the suggested future research avenues.

2. Literature review and hypotheses formulation:

The debate regarding the link between corporate governance and dividend policy is considered as a mystery, this empirical issue remains unresolved and no consensus was found. Drawing from different theoretical frameworks, either agency theory or socio-emotional wealth (SEW) perspective, one hypothesis often raised is whether family control affects corporates' dividend policy. A strand of literature argues that family ownership and control have a negative impact, while other scholars record positive effect, indeed, we will try to summaries theses opposing

and conflicting results by scrutinizing different empirical studies with various theoretical underpinnings. Focusing on a developed market where the investor protection is high and based on a balanced panel data of Australian firms covering six years, the results indicate that family control exhibits a significant positive impact on dividend payout, this shows clearly that families in the position of large shareholders act as stewards, can mitigate agency problems and lessen the risk of expropriating minority shareholders' wealth (Setia-Atmaja et al., 2009; Setia-Atmaja, 2010). In a similar vein and based on an unbalanced panel data of Japanese publicly-listed firms, the empirical results demonstrate robust negative significant impacts of family control on dividend payout, the findings can be attributed to the fact that family-controlled firms behave in the interest of minority shareholders, aim to protect the "family name" and foster the family reputation in order to attract potential investors and gain the market confidence in the case of a future need of external financing (Yoshikawa & Rasheed, 2010).

A comparative study based on large industrial listed firms in the Chinese capital market assesses that state-controlled firms have stable dividend payments in comparison to family controlled-firms, the results are explained by the fact that families are either more flexible in taking dividend decisions or because the entrenchment effect is weak, moreover, the empirical insights lend credibility to the superior power of monitoring by family blockholders due to less separation of ownership and management (T. T. He et al., 2012). Using panel data and examining a sample of nine Eurozone countries, the results document a stable and higher dividend rates of family-controlled firms, this finding is consistent with the argument that family-controlled companies use dividends as a mechanism to alleviate agency costs, thereupon decreasing the risk of using excess cash for family owners' personal interests (Pindado et al., 2012). Based on 1499 firm-year observations in the Tokyo stock exchange, the results corroborate previous studies, indicating that family members act as stewards, can discipline managers and safeguard minority shareholders' interests, in addition, more interesting results state that foreign ownership can moderate positively and strengthen the nexus between family control and dividend distributions (Sakawa & Watanabel, 2019). Along similar lines, empirical evidence from the Turkish context corroborate extant literature that family ownership affects positively the distribution of dividend, however, robustness results assess that family members' excessive participation in the board has a negative effect on the level of dividend distribution, these results could be interpreted as a negative signal to investors and lead to an increase of agency costs (Khan et al., 2022). In the same line of reasoning, and based on a large panel data set of privately-held family firms in the Italian context, the authors employed a different proxy

for family ownership by using the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index in order to capture the percentage of shares held by the largest seven family shareholders, building on this, the results report significant positive impact of family equity dispersion on the distribution of dividends, more strikingly, these empirical findings vary depending on firm leadership, environment uncertainty and the generational stage of family firms (Miller et al., 2022). On the other hand, a substantial body of the literature argue that family control has a negative effect on dividend payout. Gugler (2003) has focused on a panel of Austrian listed firms covering the period of (1991-1999), the results demonstrate that family-controlled firms do not engage in dividend smoothing practices, opt for lower target payouts ratios and they are least disinclined to cut dividends, chiefly in the case where cuts can be warranted. In contrast, Chen et al. (2005) have found that family ownership at the 10% level is positively associated with dividend payouts, conversely this relationships appears to turn negative when family ownership concentration ranges between 10% and 35% thresholds, precisely for firms with small market capitalization, this result could be interpreted by the fact that outside investors seek to demand large amount of dividend in the case of companies with high potential risk of expropriation. In a similar spirit, the results reported by Benjamin et al. (2016) corroborate the argument that when family ownership concentration reaches a high level, the risk of expropriation tends to increase which gives rise to increase the principal-principal agency conflicts.

By examining a specific context where family ownership concentration predominate the capital markets, and covering the period of (1996-2008), Huang et al. (2012) have reported that Taiwanese family-controlled firms adopt different dividend payout strategies depending on cash flow rights level, in other words, at low level, the results indicate that families tend to increase or claim more in dividends, while at a moderate or a high level of controlling families' cash flow rights, the entrenchment effect intensifies and becomes the dominant explanatory argument. Along similar lines, the study of González et al. (2014) reveals that Colombian firms with family members involved in management do not impact dividend payouts, however, family involvement through ownership or pyramidal structures exhibit negative effect on dividend payout, in fact, these findings suggest that pyramidal structure can be harmful to minority shareholders' interests thereby exacerbating agency costs. Similarly, empirical evidence from the Turkish context provide robust evidence that family governance and involvement are associated with low levels of dividend payouts (Kilincarslan, 2021; Sener & Akben Selcuk, 2019). By the same token, the Tunisian market provides strong evidence that family control has a significant negative impact on dividend payout, in addition, the results

remain robust under different tests and proxies of dividend, supporting the hypothesis that family-controlled firms suffer from lower principal-agent conflicts, moreover the study provides insights that Tunisian family-controlled firms tend to retain cash and pay less dividend in order to preserve SEW, insure long-term growth and safeguard the firm's financial stability to future generations (Hammouda & Basly, 2020). Accordingly, studies conducted in the Indonesian, Chinese and Pakistani capital markets extend this issue and confirm that family-controlled or managed firms maintain low dividend payouts and seem more interested in retaining cash rather than the argument of using dividend as mechanism to mitigate agency conflicts (Duygun et al., 2018; Herdhayinta et al., 2021; Mulyani et al., 2016; Setiawan et al., 2016; Wei et al., 2011; Yousaf et al., 2019). In the same line of reasoning, a cross-country analysis covering nine East Asian capital markets corroborate previous arguments, furthermore, it yields more interesting results, suggesting that the expropriation risk by family firms increases during turbulent periods (Crises) (Attig et al., 2016). In addition, it is noteworthy to mention that extent empirical evidence from both developed and emerging markets reveals the existence of a monotonic (U-Shaped) relationship between family control and dividend policy, in other words, the dividend payout varies depending on family ownership levels and firm's life cycle maturity (Gugler & Yurtoglu, 2003; Huang et al., 2012; Setia-Atmaja et al., 2009; Sikalidis et al., 2022). In contrast to previous studies, there are few empirical investigations who have failed to record significant impact of family ownership (Bataineh, 2021; Khan, 2021; Khan & Kent Baker, 2025), family involvement (Al-Najjar & Kilincarslan, 2016) and family governance (Herdhayinta et al., 2021) on dividend policy decisions. Following prior literature and based on the theoretical discussion above, we hypothesize that family control has a negative significant impact on dividend payout.

3. Data and methodology:

3.1. Sample selection:

The sample consists of all Moroccan listed firms in the Casablanca stock exchange, spanning the period (2019-2023). We exclude firms belonging to the banking and insurance industries due to the accounting specifications and the differences in regulation. Firms with missing data, negative book value of equity, zero sales, or not being listed during the whole study period were also eliminated. Data on ownership and board of directors were manually extracted from annual reports while data on accounting and dividend payout were directly collected based on financial statements and overview sheets of listed companies published on the websites of the Moroccan Authority of Capital Markets (AMMC) and the Casablanca Stock Exchange (CSE).

3.2. Model specification

To test our research hypotheses we follow the regression models [Pooled OLS for equation (1) and Probit/logit for equation (2)] as suggested by prior studies (Al-Najjar & Kilincarslan, 2016; Boumosleh & Cline, 2015; Duygun et al., 2018; Hammouda & Basly, 2020; Jiraporn & Lee, 2018; Khan et al., 2022; Sener & Akben Selcuk, 2019; Wei et al., 2011).

$$\text{Dividend payout}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Family control}_{it} + \sum_{j=1}^{13} \beta_{jit} \text{Control}_{jit} + \text{YEAR}_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{DIV_PAY}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Family control}_{it} + \sum_{j=1}^{13} \beta_{jit} \text{Control}_{jit} + \text{YEAR}_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

3.3. Variable measurements:

Dependent variable: Dividend payout

DIV/TA: is the ratio of total dividend to total assets (Duygun et al., 2018; Gonzalez et al., 2017; González et al., 2014; Herdhayinta et al., 2021; Jiraporn et al., 2011, 2016).

DIV-YIELD: is the ratio of the dividend per share to the closing price share (Al-Najjar & Kilincarslan, 2016; Beladi et al., 2022; Z. Chen et al., 2005; Mehdi et al., 2017; Rashid, 2016).

DIV/SALES: is the ratio of total dividend to total sales (J. He et al., 2020; Hwang et al., 2013; Jiraporn & Chintrakarn, 2009; Jiraporn & Lee, 2018; La Porta et al., 2000).

DIV-PAY : is a dummy variable that takes the value of one if the firm decides de pay dividend in the year t and zero otherwise (Al-Najjar & Kilincarslan, 2016; Deslandes et al., 2016; Duygun et al., 2018; González et al., 2014; T. T. He et al., 2012; Khan et al., 2022; Mancinelli & Ozkan, 2006; Mehdi et al., 2017; Michiels et al., 2015; Sener & Akben Selcuk, 2019).

Independent variable:

Family control: (FAM_CON) is a dummy variable that equals to one if the family has fractional equity ownership and at least one family member is on the board and zero otherwise. We adopt this measure to capture both the effect of family ownership and management (Anderson & Reeb, 2003, 2004; Miralles-Marcelo et al., 2014).

Control variables :

Based on extant literature, we outlined a set of control variables that have proven significant power of explaining the dividend policy in previous empirical studies. We include ownership concentration, board characteristics and firm level-determinants (Firm size, age, liquidity, financial performance, capital intensity, leverage, external audit quality and growth opportunities) that may influence corporates' dividend decisions. With regard to corporate

governance mechanisms, **Ownership concentration (*TOP-1*)** is the percentage of shares held by the largest shareholder (Hwang et al., 2013; Iturriaga & Crisóstomo, 2010; Mancinelli & Ozkan, 2006; Tayachi et al., 2023), **Board size (*B-SIZE*)** is the number of directors on the board (Boumosleh & Cline, 2015; J. Chen et al., 2017; Z. Chen et al., 2005; Duygun et al., 2018; González et al., 2014; Mehdi et al., 2017; Sener & Akben Selcuk, 2019), **CEO duality (*DUAL*)** is a dummy variable that equals one if both seats are held by the same person (Abor & Fiador, 2013; Hampl & Vágnerová Linnertová, 2025; Sener & Akben Selcuk, 2019; Sharma, 2011; Tahir et al., 2020), **Board independence (*IND*)** is the proportion of independent directors on the board (Benjamin et al., 2016; J. Chen et al., 2017; Z. Chen et al., 2005; Gyapong et al., 2021; Hampl & Vágnerová Linnertová, 2025; Herdhayinta et al., 2021; Sener & Akben Selcuk, 2019), **Board gender diversity (*BGD*)** is the proportion of female directors on the board (J. Chen et al., 2017; García-Meca et al., 2022; Herdhayinta et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2022; Nadia & Hanafi, 2022; Tahir et al., 2020), for corporate characteristics, we include **Firm size (*FSIZE*)** as the natural logarithm of firm's total assets (Adjaoud & Ben-Amar, 2010; Boumosleh & Cline, 2015; Gyapong et al., 2021; Hasan & Uddin, 2022; Houqe et al., 2023; Hwang et al., 2013; Jabbouri, 2016; Jiraporn et al., 2011), **Firm age (*AGE*)** is the number of years since firm's initial public offering (AlGhazali et al., 2024; Al-Najjar & Kilincarslan, 2016, 2017; Boumosleh & Cline, 2015; Dewasiri et al., 2019; González et al., 2014; Hasan & Uddin, 2022), **Liquidity (*LIQ*)** is the ratio of current assets to current liabilities (Boumlik et al., 2023; Dewasiri et al., 2019; Houqe et al., 2023; Jabbouri, 2016; Singh et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2020), **Capital intensity (*GPPE*)** is the ratio of gross property, plant and equipment to total assets (J. Chen et al., 2017; Hasan & Uddin, 2022; Houqe et al., 2023; Setia-Atmaja, 2010), **Firm performance (*ROA*)** is the ratio of operating income to total assets (AlGhazali et al., 2024; Al-Najjar & Kilincarslan, 2016; Bae et al., 2021; Beladi et al., 2022; Buertey et al., 2024; J. Chen et al., 2017; Hasan & Uddin, 2022), **Market -to-book ratio (*MTB*)** is defined as the ratio of market value of equity to the book value of equity (Abor & Fiador, 2013; Adjaoud & Ben-Amar, 2010; Deslandes et al., 2015; Dewasiri et al., 2019; Gaga et al., 2025; Houqe et al., 2023), **Audit firm size (*BIG-4*)** is a dummy variable that equals one if the firm is audited by one of the BIG-4 auditing firms and zero otherwise (DeAngelo, 1981; Fathelkhir et al., 2024; Mitton, 2004; Zahid et al., 2023) and **Leverage (*LEV*)** is the ratio of long-term debt to total assets (Benjamin et al., 2016; Boumosleh & Cline, 2015; Buertey et al., 2024; Houqe et al., 2023; Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Jiraporn et al., 2011; Setia-Atmaja, 2010; Sharma, 2011). Finally, we include year dummy variables to control for unobserved time-varying effects (Kilincarslan, 2021).

Table I: Descriptive statistics

Variables	Mean	SD	Q25	Median	Q75	Q90
DIV/TA	0,0424	0,0507	0,0000	0,0269	0,0661	0,1085
DIV-YIELD	0,0252	0,0246	0,0000	0,0230	0,0420	0,0592
DIV/SALES	0,1552	0,3987	0,0000	0,0357	0,0999	0,2684
DIV-PAY	0,6400	0,4810	0,0000	1,0000	1,0000	1,0000
FAM-CON	0,5160	0,5007	0,0000	1,0000	1,0000	1,0000
TOP-1	0,5067	0,2132	0,3700	0,5145	0,6486	0,8140
B-SIZE	8,8680	2,5903	7,0000	9,0000	10,0000	13,0000
DUAL	0,4760	0,5004	0,0000	0,0000	1,0000	1,0000
IND	0,2013	0,1426	0,1250	0,2000	0,2857	0,3750
BGD	0,1782	0,1242	0,1000	0,1667	0,2727	0,3333
FSIZE	21,0697	1,5623	20,0017	21,1669	22,2265	22,9778
AGE	24,1750	20,9254	12,5836	16,0164	24,5534	67,0671
LIQ	3,0140	3,7350	1,3770	1,9621	3,3989	5,6870
ROA	0,0699	0,0902	0,0116	0,0581	0,1286	0,1880
GPPE	0,5436	0,5205	0,0588	0,4409	0,7524	1,4627
MTB	2,6647	3,1397	0,9579	1,9783	4,3137	5,6424
BIG-4	0,4720	0,5002	0,0000	0,0000	1,0000	1,0000
LEV	0,1031	0,1160	0,0000	0,0642	0,1579	0,2936

Source: Authors

The table I presents summary statistics of all variables used in the study. Regarding the dividend payout, the dividend/total assets and the dividend yield ratios denote a mean value of 4,24% and (2,52%) respectively. The mean (median) value of dividend to sales ratio is 2,52% (2,3%). 64 per cent of firms pay dividends. The mean value of shares held by the largest shareholder is 51,60%, a 25th and 90th percentiles values of 37% and 81,4% respectively, supporting the hypothesis of high level of ownership concentration in emerging markets (Jabbouri & Naili, 2019). Regarding board characteristics, the mean value of board size is 8,86, the mean values in percentage of board independence and board gender diversity are 20,13% (17,82%) respectively. The median value of firms' size in natural logarithm is 21,06 with an average age of 24,17 years. Collateral assets (GPPE) have a mean value of 0,54 with a standard deviation of 0.52 and a median value of 1,96 for the liquidity measure. On average, our sample firms report a Return on Assets (ROA) ratio of 6,99%, a debt ratio of 10,31% and a MTB ratio of 2,66%. Almost half of our sample, (47,2%) are auditing by one of the BIG-4 auditing firms. The table II displays the correlation matrix in order to give us a primary view on the expected effects of independent variables on dividend payout. The analysis suggests that board size has a significant positive impact on dividend payout while CEO duality and board independence appeared to be negatively correlated with dividend payout. All the firm-level determinants record significant expected impacts, except liquidity. After analyzing our correlation matrix, we can confirm that multicollinearity is not an issue since all coefficients are below the threshold of 10 (Gujarati & Porter, 2009; Sener & Akben Selcuk, 2019).

Variables	DIV/TA	FAM-CON	TOP-1	B-SIZE	DUAL	B-IND	BGD	F-SIZE	AGE	LIQ	ROA	GPPE	MTB	BIG-4	LEV
DIV/TA	1														
FAM-CON	-0.197***	1													
TOP-1	0.001	0.025	1												
B-SIZE	0.154**	-0.059	-0.084	1											
DUAL	-0.236***	0.266***	0.205***	-0.277***	1										
B-IND	-0.250***	0.107*	0.003	-0.167***	0.264***	1									
BGD	0.043	-0.013	-0.040	0.060	0.022	0.034	1								
F-SIZE	0.221***	-0.103	0.027	0.454***	-0.217***	-0.059	-0.095	1							
AGE	0.127**	-0.044	0.097	0.182***	0.178***	0.027	0.040	-0.127**	1						
LIQ	-0.089	-0.015	0.153**	-0.209***	0.205***	0.235***	-0.128**	-0.286***	0.130**	1					
ROA	0.674***	-0.126**	0.089	0.040	-0.130**	-0.302***	0.119*	0.182***	0.025	-0.151**	1				
GPPE	0.267***	-0.093	0.104	0.301***	-0.017	-0.226***	-0.080	0.210***	0.188***	-0.266***	0.274***	1			
MTB	0.468***	-0.224***	0.031	0.215***	-0.097	-0.230***	0.088	0.354***	0.037	-0.133**	0.671***	0.245***	1		
BIG-4	0.053	-0.255***	0.176***	0.209***	-0.019	-0.076	-0.079	0.426***	0.089	-0.212***	0.200***	0.312***	0.214***	1	
LEV	-0.256***	0.148**	-0.017	0.100	0.065	0.224***	-0.171***	0.282***	-0.160**	-0.129**	-0.249***	0.054	-0.003	0.098	1

* Significant at 10%. ** Significant at 5%. *** Significant at 1%

Source: Authors

Table II: Correlation matrix

This table presents the correlation matrix for the dependent, independent and control variables over the period (2019-2023) **Note: DIV/TA** : Total dividend/Total assets, **FAM-CON**: A dummy variable that equals to one if the family has fractional equity ownership and at least one family member is on the board and zero otherwise, **TOP-1**: Percentage of shares held by the largest shareholder, **B-SIZE**: Number of directors on the board, **DUAL**: A dummy variable that equals to 1 if both seats are held by the same person, **IND**: Proportion of independent directors on the board, **BGD**: Proportion of female directors on the board, **F-SIZE** stands for natural logarithm of total assets, **AGE**: Number of years since firm's initial public offering (IPO), **LIQ**: Current assets/Current liabilities, **ROA**: Return on assets (Operating income scaled by total assets), **GPPE**: Gross property, plant and equipment/Total assets **MTB**: Market-to-book ratio, **BIG-4** is a dummy variable that equals one if the firm is audited by one of the BIG-4 auditing firms and zero otherwise, **LEV**: Long term debt/Total assets.

Table III: Regression of dividend payout on family control and control variables

VARIABLES	Expected Sign	OLS		
		(1) DIV/TA	(2) DIV-YIELD	(3) DIV/SALES
FAM_CON	+/-	-0.0105** (0.0049)	-0.0035 (0.0032)	-0.1953*** (0.0584)
TOP-1	+	-0.0134 (0.0093)	-0.0269*** (0.0073)	-0.4437*** (0.1426)
B-SIZE	+	0.0005 (0.0011)	0.0002 (0.0007)	0.0066 (0.0081)
DUAL	-	-0.0071 (0.0045)	-0.0014 (0.0035)	0.0699 (0.0469)
IND	+	0.0027 (0.0252)	-0.0202* (0.0121)	-0.3179* (0.1626)
BGD	+	-0.0130 (0.0188)	0.0192 (0.0125)	0.2987 (0.2056)
FSIZE	+	0.0055*** (0.0019)	0.0026** (0.0012)	0.0495*** (0.0168)
AGE	?	0.0003*** (0.0001)	0.0001* (0.0001)	-0.0026*** (0.0009)
LIQ	+	0.0012** (0.0006)	0.0005 (0.0003)	0.0499*** (0.0169)
ROA	+	0.4068*** (0.0556)	0.1876*** (0.0254)	-0.0293 (0.2601)
MTB	+/-	0.0029** (0.0012)	-0.0028*** (0.0007)	0.0002 (0.0102)
GPPE	+	0.0061 (0.0051)	-0.0003 (0.0027)	-0.0190 (0.0353)
BIG-4	+/-	-0.0221*** (0.0052)	-0.0078** (0.0035)	-0.1397*** (0.0414)
LEV	-	-0.0393* (0.0052)	-0.0067 (0.0035)	-0.0320 (0.0414)

Constant	(0.0218)	(0.0125)	(0.2298)
	-0.1067***	-0.0280	-0.7110**
Observations	(0.0381)	(0.0237)	(0.3215)
	243	243	240
R-squared	0.6445	0.3565	0.2727
Adjusted R-squared	0.6159	0.3048	0.2134
Mean VIF	1.5990	1.5990	1.5783
F-stat	17.7849***	10.0129***	2.7641***
Years FE	Yes	Yes	Yes

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Source: Authors

Table IV: Results of panel regressions using Feasible Generalized Least Square (FGLS)

VARIABLES	Expected Sign	FGLS		
		(1) DIV/TA	(2) DIV-YIELD	(3) DIV/SALES
FAM_CON	+/-	-0.0107*** (0.0027)	-0.0040* (0.0023)	-0.0617*** (0.0217)
TOP-1	+	-0.0183*** (0.0066)	-0.0276*** (0.0047)	-0.0385 (0.0505)
B-SIZE	+	-0.0003 (0.0006)	0.0001 (0.0005)	0.0012 (0.0034)
DUAL	-	-0.0021 (0.0027)	-0.0009 (0.0023)	-0.0139 (0.0203)
IND	+	0.0041 (0.0102)	-0.0228*** (0.0080)	-0.0122 (0.0841)
BGD	+	0.0071 (0.0106)	0.0088 (0.0081)	0.0088 (0.0698)
FSIZE	+	0.0064*** (0.0011)	0.0023*** (0.0008)	0.0199** (0.0078)
AGE	?	0.0004*** (0.0001)	0.0001** (0.0000)	0.0001 (0.0004)
LIQ	+	0.0008* (0.0004)	0.0001 (0.0003)	0.0167** (0.0072)
ROA	+	0.4017*** (0.0265)	0.2110*** (0.0168)	0.4770*** (0.1322)
MTB	+/-	0.0025*** (0.0008)	-0.0028*** (0.0005)	0.0001 (0.0049)
GPPE	+	0.0013 (0.0027)	-0.0030 (0.0018)	0.0022 (0.0166)
BIG-4	+/-	-0.0166*** (0.0029)	-0.0106*** (0.0021)	-0.0638*** (0.0210)
LEV	-	-0.0373***	0.0047	0.0481

Constant	(0.0128) -0.1187*** (0.0218)	(0.0090) -0.0137 (0.0170)	(0.0608) -0.3737** (0.1544)
Observations	243	243	240
Number of TKR	49	49	49
Chi2	899.1778***	399.0507***	140.5799***
Years FE	Yes	Yes	Yes

FGLS Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Source: Authors

Table V: Results of probit and logit models estimates

VARIABLES	Expected Sign	Probit	Logit
		(1) DIV-PAY	(1) DIV-PAY
FAM_CON	+/-	-0.0411 (0.2594)	-0.1143 (0.5401)
TOP-1	+	-1.6332*** (0.5482)	-3.1382*** (1.0825)
B-SIZE	+	0.1107* (0.0590)	0.1759* (0.1068)
DUAL	-	0.4872* (0.2681)	0.8778* (0.4849)
IND	+	-3.1848** (1.2489)	-5.7413** (2.8843)
BGD	+	-0.7936 (1.0257)	-1.4306 (1.8925)
FSIZE	+	0.4870*** (0.1263)	0.8553*** (0.2350)
AGE	?	0.0045 (0.0061)	0.0078 (0.0124)
LIQ	+	0.0271 (0.0365)	0.0507 (0.0664)
ROA	+	13.6096*** (3.1527)	25.6177*** (7.2265)
MTB	+/-	0.2558*** (0.0903)	0.4352*** (0.1687)
GPPE	+	0.5546** (0.2679)	1.0013** (0.5049)
BIG-4	+/-	-1.2203*** (0.2932)	-2.0627*** (0.5590)
LEV	-	-1.1854	-1.7198

Constant	(1.2671) -11.6313*** (2.4885)	(2.4216) -20.3211*** (4.6374)
Observations	243	243
Pseudo R-squared	0.4780	0.4818
Chi2	70.0449***	52.4681***
Years FE	Yes	Yes

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Source: Authors

4. Results and discussion:

The adjusted R-Squared of the pooled OLS models are 61,59%, 30,48% and 21,34% respectively. The adjusted R-Squared suggest that 61,59% of the overall variation in dividend payout are explained by the independent and control variables used in our study. In light of the pooled OLS estimated models reported in Table III, the multivariate regression results indicate that family control has a significant negative impact on two proxies of dividend payout ratios (DIV/TA and DIV/SALES) at the 5% and the 1% levels respectively. Although the effect is negative, it lacks statistical significance when using the dividend yield as a proxy. The empirical results are aligned with the findings of extant literature and gives partial support for the agency theory predictions (Al-Najjar & Kilincarslan, 2016; Attig et al., 2016; Benjamin et al., 2016; Z. Chen et al., 2005; Duygun et al., 2018; González et al., 2014; Gugler, 2003; Hammouda & Basly, 2020; Huang et al., 2012; Kilincarslan, 2021; Mulyani et al., 2016; Sener & Akben Selcuk, 2019; Setiawan et al., 2016; Wei et al., 2011; Wu et al., 2020; Yousaf et al., 2019).

To deal with heteroscedasticity concerns and ensure the robustness of our results , we employed (FGLS) estimator (Sakawa & Watanabel, 2019; Yoshikawa & Rasheed, 2010) and we can confirm that our results are robust and significant at the 1% level for two different proxies of dividend payouts [Column (1) and Colum (3)] of Table IV and at the 10% threshold for the dividend yield. The negative relationship between family control and dividend payout could be explained by several reasons, first of all, agency costs and information asymmetries are considered to be quasi-absent in family controlled firms due to less separation of management and ownership, “*the residual claimants bearing (nearly) all of the costs and receiving (nearly) all of the benefits of their actions,*”, which gives rise to a better and efficient monitoring, this argument justifies that dividend seems to be less valuable when family holds the position of a largest shareholder, thereby providing support for the alignment effect (González et al., 2014;

Gugler, 2003; T. T. He et al., 2012; Sikalidis et al., 2022), in a parallel manner, managers of family firms are presumed to be focusing on investing in projects that ensure firm value maximization rather than wasting retained cash in non-profitable projects (Pindado et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2020). In the same line of reasoning and from a SEW perspective, family shareholders have incentives to avoid any negative issues that could harm the “family name” and reputation (Gomez-Mejia et al., 2011), furthermore, Deslandes et al. (2016) and Hammouda & Basly (2020) claim that family-controlled firms’ desire to hold liquidity is motivated by their ability to guarantee future financing needs, in plain terms, the aim of the controlling family is to ensure the firm’s long-term growth and longevity by considering the firm as a legacy and a heritage that should be transmitted to future generations while maintaining control (Deslandes et al., 2016; Gomez-Mejia et al., 2011). On the other hand, the negative impact of family control on dividend payouts is interpreted in previous studies by the potential risk of extracting benefits from minority shareholders by large family owners, which leads to intensify the principal-principal conflicts (type II Agency costs), leading to the risk of the entrenchment effect by using retained cash for private benefits (Al-Najjar & Kilincarslan, 2016; Attig et al., 2016; Duygun et al., 2018; Sener & Akben Selcuk, 2019; Wei et al., 2011; Yoshikawa & Rasheed, 2010). Given the nature of our dependent variable (DIV-PAY), probit and logistic regression models were performed in order to assess the effect of family control on the propensity of paying dividends. The logit and probit estimates highlight that family control is associated negatively to the propensity of paying dividends, however, it does not reach statistical significance (Table V, [column (1) and Column (2)], thus we fail to support out hypothesis, similar results were found in the study of Al-Najjar & Kilincarslan (2016). **It warrants consideration that without having sufficient data and deep empirical investigations of agency costs (Type II)**, our results are still limited and could mislead the reality about large family shareholders, therefore fail to corroborate or lend credibility to the arguments of entrenchment or expropriation hypotheses implying that low dividend payouts could be interpreted as an increase of moral hazard between controlling and minority shareholders (Al-Najjar & Kilincarslan, 2016; Setia-Atmaja et al., 2009). Regarding control variables, ownership concentration appears to be negatively related to dividend payout, which is consistent with previous studies (Gonzalez et al., 2017; Gyapong et al., 2021; Kilincarslan, 2021; Mancinelli & Ozkan, 2006; Mehdi et al., 2017; Tayachi et al., 2023). For board of directors’ characteristics, board size has a slight significant impact on the propensity of paying dividends and join the findings of a recent study conducted in the Moroccan context by Louziri & Oubal (2025). In contrast, independent

directors on the board are negatively related to dividend payouts, a surprising and striking result, that deviates from previous empirical outcomes (J. Chen et al., 2017; Gyapong et al., 2021; Setia-Atmaja et al., 2009; Sharma, 2011), our findings challenge the monitoring hypothesis of board independence. CEO duality and board gender diversity were insignificant in our study, therefore the hypotheses are rejected. Concerning firm attributes, unsurprisingly, larger and more profitable firms prove higher capacity of claiming more dividends, these results are in accordance with empirical findings conducted in different contexts (Abor & Fiador, 2013; AlGhazali et al., 2024; Al-Najjar & Kilincarslan, 2016; Bae et al., 2021; Buertey et al., 2024; Hammouda & Basly, 2020; Hampl & Vágnerová Linnertová, 2025). As expected, firm age, liquidity and capital intensity are associated with dividend intensity levels and the propensity of paying dividends, the results are consistent with numerous studies (Al-Najjar & Kilincarslan, 2016; Ananzeh et al., 2025; Boumosleh & Cline, 2015; Hasan & Uddin, 2022; Jabbouri, 2016; Mehdi et al., 2017; Singh et al., 2023). Furthermore, the regression results indicated that firms with high growth opportunities are positively associated with dividend payouts, a result that contradicts previous empirical works (Ananzeh et al., 2025; Hasan & Uddin, 2022; Rozeff, 1982; Sharma, 2011) but in accordance with a strand of literature (Abor & Fiador, 2013; Boumlik et al., 2023; Duygun et al., 2018; Jiraporn & Lee, 2018; Le et al., 2026; Louziri & Oubal, 2025; Pindado et al., 2012). The leverage variable behaves as expected and provide partial support for our hypothesis (Beladi et al., 2022; Jabbouri, 2016; Jensen, 1986).

5. Conclusion:

Our study is based on balanced panel data covering a five-year period, the empirical insights reveal that family-controlled firms employ low levels of dividend payouts, in particular, our findings are in accordance with previous literature, supporting the hypothesis that family-controlled firms face lower levels of type I agency costs, which lends support to a more conservative dividend policy. Nevertheless, our study suffers from various limitations, first of all, the sample size is small, thus the external validity of our results is limited and the interpretation should be done in a cautious way. Secondly, we suggest to use other proxies of family control based on the percentage of shares held by family members in order to test the potential non-linear (U-shaped) effect (Benjamin et al., 2016; Z. Chen et al., 2005; González et al., 2014; Huang et al., 2012; Sener & Akben Selcuk, 2019; Setia-Atmaja et al., 2009; Setiawan et al., 2016; Sikalidis et al., 2022). Furthermore, future studies might consider the use of other proxies of dividend policy (i.e, dividend payout stability, changes or dividend smoothing) (Attig et al., 2016; Gugler, 2003; T. T. He et al., 2012; Pindado et al., 2012), moreover, an analysis of

pre and post-crisis also could be investigated in order to demystify family-controlled firms' behavior in the wake of crises (Mehdi et al., 2017; Sikalidis et al., 2022). To account for potential endogeneity issues, we recommend upcoming research the application of two-stages least-squares estimation technique (2SLS) (González et al., 2014; Herdhayinta et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2020), simultaneous equation system (3SLS) (Mulyani et al., 2016; Setia-Atmaja et al., 2009) or dynamic panel data using GMM (Mehdi et al., 2017; Pindado et al., 2012; Setiawan et al., 2016; Yousaf et al., 2019). With respect to corporate governance variables, further investigations should consider the inclusion of institutional, bank, state or foreign ownership (Acero Fraile & Alcalde Fradejas, 2014; Al-Najjar & Kilincarslan, 2016; Duygun et al., 2018; Gugler, 2003; Gugler & Yurtoglu, 2003; T. T. He et al., 2012; Hwang et al., 2013; Sakawa & Watanabel, 2019; Setiawan et al., 2016; Short et al., 2002; Yoshikawa & Rasheed, 2010). Complementarily, our empirical insights give partial explanation of the nexus between family control and dividend policy, indeed, further empirical work could reinforce our results by exploring the expropriation or entrenchment hypothesis related to Type II agency costs, in particular, shedding the light on the moderating effect of free cash flow (Adjaoud & Ben-Amar, 2010; Attig et al., 2016; Jensen, 1986; Le et al., 2026), growth opportunities (Benjamin et al., 2016; Kilincarslan, 2021; Sener & Akben Selcuk, 2019; Sikalidis et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2020; Yoshikawa & Rasheed, 2010), financial constraints and R&D expenditures (Gugler, 2003; Gugler & Yurtoglu, 2003). Lastly, we suggest the extension of the sample by including other country belonging to the MENA region in order to foster the empirical results' robustness. Our empirical results contribute to the debate by enhancing understanding of agency problems within family-controlled firm, furthermore, our findings shed light on the role of corporate governance mechanisms in shaping dividend policy decisions in the Moroccan context and also offer valuable insights for investors and regulators.

References:

- Abor, J., & Fiador, V. (2013). Does corporate governance explain dividend policy in Sub-Saharan Africa? *International Journal of Law and Management*, 55(3), 201-225. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17542431311327637>
- Acero Fraile, I., & Alcalde Fradejas, N. (2014). Ownership structure and board composition in a high ownership concentration context. *European Management Journal*, 32(4), 646-657. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2013.10.003>
- Adjaoud, F., & Ben-Amar, W. (2010). Corporate Governance and Dividend Policy: Shareholders' Protection or Expropriation? *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 37(5-6), 648-667. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-5957.2010.02192.x>
- Aivazian, V., Booth, L., & Cleary, S. (2003). Dividend policy and the organization of capital markets. *Journal of Multinational Financial Management*, 13(2), 101-121. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1042-444X\(02\)00038-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1042-444X(02)00038-5)
- AlGhazali, A., Al-Yahyaee, K. H., Fairchild, R., & Guney, Y. (2024). What do dividend changes reveal? Theory and evidence from a unique environment. *Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting*, 62(2), 499-552. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11156-023-01211-x>
- Al-Najjar, B., & Kilincarslan, E. (2016). The effect of ownership structure on dividend policy: Evidence from Turkey. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 16(1), 135-161. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-09-2015-0129>
- Al-Najjar, B., & Kilincarslan, E. (2017). Corporate dividend decisions and dividend smoothing: New evidence from an empirical study of Turkish firms. *International Journal of Managerial Finance*, 13(3), 304-331. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJMF-10-2016-0191>
- Ananzeh, H., Khalifeh, A., Alqudah, H., Al-Ababneh, H. A., & Al Amosh, H. (2025). ESG rating, corporate dividends policy, and the moderating role of corporate life cycle: Cross country study. *International Studies of Economics*, 20(3), 297-321. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ise3.104>
- Anderson, R. C., & Reeb, D. M. (2003). Founding-Family Ownership and Firm Performance: Evidence from the S&P 500. *The Journal of Finance*, 58(3), 1301-1328. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1540-6261.00567>
- Anderson, R. C., & Reeb, D. M. (2004). Board Composition: Balancing Family Influence in S&P 500 Firms. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 49(2), 209-237. <https://doi.org/10.2307/4131472>
- Attig, N., Boubakri, N., El Ghouli, S., & Guedhami, O. (2016). The Global Financial Crisis, Family Control, and Dividend Policy. *Financial Management*, 45(2), 291-313. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fima.12115>
- Bae, K.-H., El Ghouli, S., Guedhami, O., & Zheng, X. (2021). Board Reforms and Dividend Policy: International Evidence. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 56(4), 1296-1320. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022109020000319>
- Bataineh, H. (2021). The impact of ownership structure on dividend policy of listed firms in Jordan. *Cogent Business & Management*, 8(1), 1863175. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2020.1863175>
- Beladi, H., Hu, M., Li, S., & Yang, J. (2022). Dual-class share structure on the dividend payout policy: Evidence from China Concepts Stocks. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 82, 102212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2022.102212>
- Benjamin, S. J., Wasiuzzaman, S., Mokhtarinia, H., & Rezaie Nejad, N. (2016). Family ownership and dividend payout in Malaysia. *International Journal of Managerial Finance*, 12(3), 314-334. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJMF-08-2014-0114>

- Boumlik, Z., Oulhadj, B., & Colot, O. (2023). The Effect of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Corporate Dividend Policy of Moroccan Listed Firms. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 16(8), 350. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm16080350>
- Boumosleh, A., & Cline, B. N. (2015). Outside Director Stock Options and Dividend Policy. *Journal of Financial Services Research*, 47(3), 381-410. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10693-013-0174-2>
- Buertey, S., Nguyen, H. T., & Thompson, E. K. (2024). The audit committee and dividend policy : An empirical study of the post-SOX era. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 24(2), 346-364. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-10-2022-0408>
- Chen, J., Leung, W. S., & Goergen, M. (2017). The impact of board gender composition on dividend payouts. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 43, 86-105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2017.01.001>
- Chen, Z., Cheung, Y.-L., Stouraitis, A., & Wong, A. W. S. (2005). Ownership concentration, firm performance, and dividend policy in Hong Kong. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, 13(4), 431-449. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pacfin.2004.12.001>
- DeAngelo, L. E. (1981). Auditor size and audit quality. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 3(3), Article 3. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-4101\(81\)90002-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-4101(81)90002-1)
- Deslandes, M., Fortin, A., & Landry, S. (2016). Payout differences between family and nonfamily listed firms : A socioemotional wealth perspective. *Journal of Family Business Management*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFBM-05-2015-0020>
- Deslandes, M., Landry, S., & Fortin, A. (2015). The effects of a tax dividend cut on payout policies : Canadian evidence. *International Journal of Managerial Finance*, 11(1), 2-22. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJMF-05-2014-0081>
- Dewasiri, N. J., Yatiwelle Koralalage, W. B., Abdul Azeez, A., Jayarathne, P. G. S. A., Kuruppuarachchi, D., & Weerasinghe, V. A. (2019). Determinants of dividend policy : Evidence from an emerging and developing market. *Managerial Finance*, 45(3), 413-429. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MF-09-2017-0331>
- Duygun, M., Guney, Y., & Moin, A. (2018). Dividend policy of Indonesian listed firms : The role of families and the state. *Economic Modelling*, 75, 336-354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econmod.2018.07.007>
- Easterbrook, F. H. (1984). Two Agency-Cost Explanations of Dividends. *The American Economic Review*, 74(4), 650-659.
- Faccio, M., Lang, L. H. P., & Young, L. (2001). Dividends and Expropriation. *The American Economic Review*, 91(1), 54-78.
- Fama, E. F., & Jensen, M. C. (1985). Organizational forms and investment decisions. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 14(1), 101-119. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X\(85\)90045-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X(85)90045-5)
- Farinha, J. (2003). Dividend Policy, Corporate Governance and the Managerial Entrenchment Hypothesis : An Empirical Analysis. *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 30(9-10), 1173-1209. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0306-686X.2003.05624.x>
- Fathelkhir, N., Karam, S., & Gaga, O. (2024). Do BIG-4 auditors perform a corporate governance role in the Moroccan context? Evidence from accounting and market-based performance measures. *African Scientific Journal*, 3(26), 767-792. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14025066>
- Gaga, O., Karam, S., & Fathelkhir, N. (2025). Strengthening the Corporate Governance System through Financial Reporting Quality : Evidence from Accounting Conservatism in an Emerging Market. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance, Auditing, Management and Economics*, 6(5), Article 5. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15514407>

- García-Meca, E., López-Iturriaga, F. J., & Santana-Martín, D. J. (2022). Board gender diversity and dividend payout : The critical mass and the family ties effect. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 79, 101973. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2021.101973>
- Gomez-Mejia, L. R., Cruz, C., Berrone, P., & De Castro, J. (2011). The Bind that Ties : Socioemotional Wealth Preservation in Family Firms. *Academy of Management Annals*, 5(1), 653-707. <https://doi.org/10.5465/19416520.2011.593320>
- González, M., Guzmán, A., Pombo, C., & Trujillo, M.-A. (2014). Family Involvement and Dividend Policy in Closely Held Firms. *Family Business Review*, 27(4), 365-385. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894486514538448>
- Gonzalez, M., Molina, C. A., Pablo, E., & Rosso, J. W. (2017). The effect of ownership concentration and composition on dividends : Evidence from Latin America. *Emerging Markets Review*, 30, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ememar.2016.08.018>
- Gugler, K. (2003). Corporate governance, dividend payout policy, and the interrelation between dividends, R&D, and capital investment. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 27(7), 1297-1321. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4266\(02\)00258-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4266(02)00258-3)
- Gugler, K., & Yurtoglu, B. B. (2003). Corporate governance and dividend pay-out policy in Germany. *European Economic Review*, 47(4), 731-758. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0014-2921\(02\)00291-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0014-2921(02)00291-X)
- Gujarati, D. N., & Porter, D. C. (2009). *Basic econometrics* (5th ed). McGraw-Hill Irwin.
- Gyapong, E., Ahmed, A., Ntim, C. G., & Nadeem, M. (2021). Board gender diversity and dividend policy in Australian listed firms : The effect of ownership concentration. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 38(2), 603-643. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10490-019-09672-2>
- Hammouda, A., & Basly, S. (2020). Socioemotional Wealth, Corporate Governance and Dividend Payout Decisions in Family Firms: Evidence from listed firms in Tunisia. *Management & Prospective*, 37(5), 17-41. <https://doi.org/10.3917/g2000.375.0017>
- HAMPL, F., & Vágnerová Linnertová, D. (2025). How the interaction between board gender diversity and ESG shapes dividend policy. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 32(2), 2472-2490. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.3068>
- Hasan, M. M., & Uddin, M. R. (2022). Do intangibles matter for corporate policies? Evidence from organization capital and corporate payout choices. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 135, 106395. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbankfin.2021.106395>
- He, J., Tian, X., Yang, H., & Zuo, L. (2020). Asymmetric Cost Behavior and Dividend Policy. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 58(4), 989-1021. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-679X.12328>
- He, T. T., Li, W. X. B., & Tang, G. Y. N. (2012). Dividends Behavior in State- Versus Family-Controlled Firms : Evidence from Hong Kong. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 110(1), 97-112. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-011-1150-0>
- Herdhayinta, H., Lau, J., & Shen, C. H. (2021). Family Female Directors versus Non-family Female Directors : Effects on Firm Value and Dividend Payouts in an Extreme Institutional Environment. *British Journal of Management*, 32(4), 969-987. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8551.12530>
- Houqe, M. N., Monem, R. M., & van Zijl, T. (2023). Business strategy, cash holdings, and dividend payouts. *Accounting & Finance*, 63(4), 3999-4035. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acfi.13082>
- Huang, Y., Chen, A., & Kao, L. (2012). Corporate governance in Taiwan : The nonmonotonic relationship between family ownership and dividend policy. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 29(1), 39-58. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10490-011-9279-z>
- Hwang, L.-S., Kim, H., Park, K., & Park, R. S. (2013). Corporate governance and payout policy : Evidence from Korean business groups. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, 24, 179-198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pacfin.2013.04.006>

- Iturriaga, F. J. L., & Crisóstomo, V. L. (2010). Do Leverage, Dividend Payout, and Ownership Concentration Influence Firms' Value Creation? An Analysis of Brazilian Firms. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 46(3), 80-94. <https://doi.org/10.2753/REE1540-496X460306>
- Jabbouri, I. (2016). Determinants of corporate dividend policy in emerging markets : Evidence from MENA stock markets. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 37, 283-298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2016.01.018>
- Jabbouri, I., & Naili, M. (2019). Does ownership concentration affect cost of debt? Evidence from an emerging market. *Review of Behavioral Finance*, 12(3), 282-296. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RBF-10-2018-0106>
- Jensen, M. C. (1986). Agency Costs of Free Cash Flow, Corporate Finance, and Takeovers. *The American Economic Review*, 76(2), 323-329.
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm : Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305-360. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X\(76\)90026-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X(76)90026-X)
- Jiraporn, P., & Chintrakarn, P. (2009). Staggered Boards, Managerial Entrenchment, and Dividend Policy. *Journal of Financial Services Research*, 36(1), 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10693-009-0059-6>
- Jiraporn, P., Kim, J.-C., & Kim, Y. S. (2011). Dividend Payouts and Corporate Governance Quality : An Empirical Investigation. *Financial Review*, 46(2), 251-279. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6288.2011.00299.x>
- Jiraporn, P., & Lee, S. M. (2018). Do Co-Opted Directors Influence Dividend Policy? *Financial Management*, 47(2), 349-381. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fima.12196>
- Jiraporn, P., Leelalai, V., & Tong, S. (2016). The effect of managerial ability on dividend policy : How do talented managers view dividend payouts? *Applied Economics Letters*, 23(12), 857-862. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504851.2015.1114572>
- Khan, A. (2021). Ownership structure, board characteristics and dividend policy : Evidence from Turkey. *Corporate Governance: The international journal of business in society*, 22(2), 340-363. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-04-2021-0129>
- Khan, A., & Kent Baker, H. (2025). Board diversity and dividend policy in India. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 42(2), 887-918. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10490-023-09922-4>
- Khan, A., Yilmaz, M. K., & Aksoy, M. (2022). Does board demographic diversity affect the dividend payout policy in Turkey? *EuroMed Journal of Business*, 19(2), 276-297. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EMJB-01-2022-0019>
- Kilincarslan, E. (2021). The influence of board independence on dividend policy in controlling agency problems in family firms. *International Journal of Accounting & Information Management*, 29(4), 552-582. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJAIM-03-2021-0056>
- La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (2000). Agency Problems and Dividend Policies around the World. *The Journal of Finance*, 55(1), 1-33. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0022-1082.00199>
- Lakssoumi, F., & Moussa, A. (2022). Indépendance, diversité du genre du conseil et qualité de l'information financière : Le rôle modérateur du contrôle familial. *Recherches en Sciences de Gestion*, 148(1), 119-146. <https://doi.org/10.3917/resg.148.0119>
- Le, A.-T., Tran, T. P., & Vu, P.-L. (2026). ESG reputational risk and corporate dividend policy : International evidence. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 106, 102246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intfin.2025.102246>
- Louzirri, R., & Oubal, K. (2025). Characteristics of the Chairman of the Board of Directors and Their Impact on Dividend Payments in the Moroccan Stock Exchange. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 18(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm18020070>

- Mancinelli, L., & Ozkan, A. (2006). Ownership structure and dividend policy : Evidence from Italian firms. *The European Journal of Finance*, 12(3), 265-282. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13518470500249365>
- Mehdi, M., Sahut, J.-M., & Teulon, F. (2017). Do corporate governance and ownership structure impact dividend policy in emerging market during financial crisis? *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 18(3), 274-297. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAAR-07-2014-0079>
- Michiels, A., Voordeckers, W., Lybaert, N., & Steijvers, T. (2015). Dividends and family governance practices in private family firms. *Small Business Economics*, 44(2), 299-314. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-014-9594-0>
- Miller, D., Amore, M. D., Quarato, F., & Corbetta, G. (2022). Family Ownership Dispersion and Dividend Payout in Family Firms. *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 13(3), 100436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfbs.2021.100436>
- Miralles-Marcelo, J. L., Miralles-Quirós, M. D. M., & Lisboa, I. (2014). The impact of family control on firm performance : Evidence from Portugal and Spain. *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 5(2), 156-168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfbs.2014.03.002>
- Mitton, T. (2004). Corporate governance and dividend policy in emerging markets. *Emerging Markets Review*, 5(4), 409-426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ememar.2004.05.003>
- Mulyani, E., Singh, H., & Mishra, S. (2016). Dividends, leverage, and family ownership in the emerging Indonesian market. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 43, 16-29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intfin.2016.03.004>
- Nadia, L. P., & Hanafi, M. M. (2022). Do women board members affect dividend policy and cash holdings? Evidence from ASEAN emerging economies. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 23(4), 705-722. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-01-2022-0011>
- Pindado, J., Requejo, I., & De La Torre, C. (2012). Do Family Firms Use Dividend Policy as a Governance Mechanism? Evidence from the Euro zone. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 20(5), 413-431. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8683.2012.00921.x>
- Rashid, A. (2016). Managerial Ownership and Agency Cost: Evidence from Bangladesh. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 137(3), 609-621. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-015-2570-z>
- Rozeff, M. S. (1982). Growth, Beta and Agency Costs as Determinants of Dividend Payout Ratios. *Journal of Financial Research*, 5(3), 249-259. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-6803.1982.tb00299.x>
- Sakawa, H., & Watanabel, N. (2019). Family control and ownership monitoring in Stakeholder-oriented corporate governance. *Management Decision*, 57(7), 1712-1728. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-04-2018-0480>
- Sener, P., & Akben Selcuk, E. (2019). Family involvement, corporate governance and dividends in Turkey. *Managerial Finance*, 45(5), 602-621. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MF-01-2018-0011>
- Setia-Atmaja, L. (2010). Dividend and debt policies of family controlled firms : The impact of board independence. *International Journal of Managerial Finance*, 6(2), 128-142. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17439131011032059>
- Setia-Atmaja, L., Tanewski, G. A., & Skully, M. (2009). The Role of Dividends, Debt and Board Structure in the Governance of Family Controlled Firms. *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 36(7-8), 863-898. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-5957.2009.02151.x>
- Setiawan, D., Bandi, B., Kee Phua, L., & Trinugroho, I. (2016). Ownership structure and dividend policy in Indonesia. *Journal of Asia Business Studies*, 10(3), 230-252. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JABS-05-2015-0053>
- Sharma, V. (2011). Independent directors and the propensity to pay dividends. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 17(4), 1001-1015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2011.05.003>

- Short, H., Zhang, H., & Keasey, K. (2002). The link between dividend policy and institutional ownership. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 8(2), 105-122. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0929-1199\(01\)00030-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0929-1199(01)00030-X)
- Sikalidis, A., Bozos, K., Chantziaras, A., & Grose, C. (2022). Influences of family ownership on dividend policy under mandatory dividend rules. *Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting*, 59(3), 939-967. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11156-022-01064-w>
- Singh, R., Gupta, C. P., & Chaudhary, P. (2023). Dividend policy and corporate life cycle : A study of Indian companies. *Managerial Finance*, 49(11), 1722-1749. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MF-01-2023-0053>
- Tahir, H., Masri, R., & Rahman, M. M. (2020). Impact of board attributes on the firm dividend payout policy : Evidence from Malaysia. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 20(5), 919-937. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-03-2020-0091>
- Tayachi, T., Hunjra, A. I., Jones, K., Mehmood, R., & Al-Faryan, M. A. S. (2023). How does ownership structure affect the financing and dividend decisions of firm? *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, 21(3), 729-746. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRA-09-2021-0291>
- Truong, T., & Heaney, R. (2007). Largest shareholder and dividend policy around the world. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 47(5), 667-687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.qref.2007.09.002>
- Wei, Z., Wu, S., Li, C., & Chen, W. (2011). Family control, institutional environment and cash dividend policy : Evidence from China. *China Journal of Accounting Research*, 4(1-2), 29-46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjar.2011.04.001>
- Wu, M., Ni, Y., & Huang, P. (2020). Dividend payouts and family-controlled firms—The effect of culture on business. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 75, 221-228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.qref.2019.03.004>
- Yoshikawa, T., & Rasheed, A. A. (2010). Family Control and Ownership Monitoring in Family-Controlled Firms in Japan. *Journal of Management Studies*, 47(2), 274-295. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6486.2009.00891.x>
- Yousaf, I., Ali, S., & Hassan, A. (2019). Effect of family control on corporate dividend policy of firms in Pakistan. *Financial Innovation*, 5(1), 42.
- Zahid, R. M. A., Taran, A., Khan, M. K., & Chersan, I.-C. (2023). ESG, dividend payout policy and the moderating role of audit quality : Empirical evidence from Western Europe. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 23(2), 350-367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bir.2022.10.012>